

ON LEONARDO p -NUMBERS

Elif Tan

Department of Mathematics, Ankara University, Ankara, Turkey
 etan@ankara.edu.tr

Ho-Hon Leung

Department of Mathematical Sciences, UAEU, Al-Ain, United Arab Emirates
 hohon.leung@uaeu.ac.ae

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce a new generalization of Leonardo numbers, which are so-called Leonardo p -numbers. We investigate some basic properties of these numbers. We also define incomplete Leonardo p -numbers which generalize the incomplete Leonardo numbers.

1. Introduction

There are several generalizations of Fibonacci numbers, one among them is Fibonacci p -numbers which are defined by Stakhov and Rozin [14]. For any given integer $p > 0$, the *Fibonacci p -numbers* are defined by the recurrence relation

$$F_{p,n} = F_{p,n-1} + F_{p,n-p-1}, \quad n > p,$$

with initial values $F_{p,0} = 0$, $F_{p,k} = 1$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, p$. The *Lucas p -numbers* also satisfy the same recurrence relation

$$L_{p,n} = L_{p,n-1} + L_{p,n-p-1}, \quad n > p,$$

but begin with initial values $L_{p,0} = p + 1$, $L_{p,k} = 1$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, p$. It is clear to see that when $p = 1$, the Fibonacci p -sequence and the Lucas p -sequence reduce to the Fibonacci sequence $\{F_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ and Lucas sequence $\{L_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$, respectively. A connection between Fibonacci p -numbers and Lucas p -numbers is

$$L_{p,n} = F_{p,n+1} + pF_{p,n-p}. \quad (1)$$

For details related to Fibonacci p -numbers and their generalizations, see [1, 10, 14, 15, 16].

On the other hand, the *Leonardo sequence* $\{\mathcal{L}_n\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is defined by the following non-homogenous recurrence relation:

$$\mathcal{L}_n = \mathcal{L}_{n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{n-2} + 1, \quad n \geq 2,$$

with initial values $\mathcal{L}_0 = \mathcal{L}_1 = 1$. In 1981, Dijkstra [7] used these numbers as an integral part of his sorting algorithm. Also the n th Leonardo number corresponds to the number of nodes in the Fibonacci tree of order n . The properties of Leonardo numbers are studied in papers written by Catarino and Borges [5, 6], Alp and Kocer [2], and Shannon [13]. Several different versions of Leonardo-like sequences were previously studied by various researchers [3, 4, 8, 9, 17]. Some of these are listed in the On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (for example, the sequence [A111314] in the On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences [12]). For the history of the Leonardo sequences, see also [A001595] in the On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences [12].

Recently, Kuhapatanakul and Chobson [11] have introduced a generalization of the Leonardo sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{k,n}\}_{n=0}^\infty$ as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{k,n} = \mathcal{L}_{k,n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{k,n-2} + k, \quad n \geq 2,$$

with initial values $\mathcal{L}_{k,0} = \mathcal{L}_{k,1} = 1$. It is clear to see that when $k = 1$, it reduces to the Leonardo sequence. When $k = 2$, this sequence reduces to the sequence [A111314] in the On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences [12].

In this article, we consider a new generalization of Leonardo sequence and investigate some basic properties of this sequence.

2. Main Results

We start by giving the definition of the Leonardo p -sequence.

Definition 1. For any given integer $p > 0$, the Leonardo p -sequence $\{\mathcal{L}_{p,n}\}_{n=0}^\infty$ is defined by the following non-homogenous relation:

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1} + p, \quad n > p,$$

with initial values $\mathcal{L}_{p,0} = \mathcal{L}_{p,1} = \dots = \mathcal{L}_{p,p} = 1$.

Some special cases for the Leonardo p -sequence can be given as follows. We note that for $p > 1$, the Leonardo p -sequences are new in OEIS.

- For $p = 1$, we get the classical Leonardo sequence.
- For $p = 2$, the first twenty Leonardo 2-numbers are

$$1, 1, 1, 4, 7, 10, 16, 25, 37, 55, 82, 121, 178, 262, 385, 565, 829, 1216, 1783, 2614.$$

- For $p = 3$, the first twenty Leonardo 3-numbers are

$$1, 1, 1, 5, 9, 13, 17, 25, 37, 53, 73, 101, 141, 197, 273, 377, 521, 721, 997, 1377.$$

- For odd p , Leonardo p -numbers are odd for all n .

The non-homogenous recurrence relation of Leonardo p -numbers can be converted to the following homogenous recurrence relation:

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1} + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p} - \mathcal{L}_{p,n-2p-1}, \quad n > 2p.$$

Similar to the relation between the Leonardo numbers and the Fibonacci numbers, now we give a relation between the Leonardo p -numbers and the Fibonacci p -numbers.

Theorem 1. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = (p + 1) F_{p,n+1} - p.$$

Proof. The proof can be done by using induction on n . It is clear to check that the relation is true for $n = 0, 1, \dots, p$. Suppose that the statement is true for all $n > p$. From the induction hypothesis, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+1} &= \mathcal{L}_{p,n} + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p} + p \\ &= (p + 1) F_{p,n+1} - p + (p + 1) F_{p,n-p+1} - p + p \\ &= (p + 1) (F_{p,n+1} + F_{p,n-p+1}) - p \\ &= (p + 1) F_{p,n+2} - p, \end{aligned}$$

which shows that the relation is true for $n + 1$. □

Remark 1. If we take $p = 1$ in Theorem 1, we get the identity

$$\mathcal{L}_n = 2F_{n+1} - 1,$$

which is given in [5, Equation 10].

The following result gives a link between the Leonardo p -numbers, the Fibonacci p -numbers, and the Lucas p -numbers.

Proposition 1. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = L_{p,n+p+1} - F_{p,n+p+1} - p.$$

Proof. By using the Equation (1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{p,n} &= (p + 1) F_{p,n+1} - p \\ &= L_{p,n+p+1} - F_{p,n+p+2} + F_{p,n+1} - p \\ &= L_{p,n+p+1} - F_{p,n+p+1} - p. \end{aligned}$$

□

Now we state a summation formula for the Leonardo p -numbers.

Proposition 2. *For $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,k} = \mathcal{L}_{p,n+p+1} - (n+1)p - 1.$$

Proof. By using Theorem 1 and by using the sum formula of Fibonacci p -numbers in [16, Property 6], we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,k} &= \sum_{k=0}^n ((p+1)F_{p,k+1} - p) \\ &= (p+1) \sum_{k=0}^n F_{p,k+1} - \sum_{k=0}^n p \\ &= (p+1) \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} F_{p,k} - (n+1)p \\ &= (p+1)(F_{p,n+p+2} - F_{p,p} - F_{p,0}) - (n+1)p \\ &= (p+1)(F_{p,n+p+2} - 1) - (n+1)p \\ &= (p+1)F_{p,n+p+2} - p - 1 - (n+1)p \\ &= \mathcal{L}_{p,n+p+1} - (n+1)p - 1. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 2. If we take $p = 1$ in Proposition 2, we get the identity

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \mathcal{L}_k = \mathcal{L}_{n+2} - (n+2),$$

which is given in [5, Proposition 3.1 (1)].

The following summation identity is true.

Theorem 2. *For $n \geq 0$ and $m = 0, 1, \dots, p - 1$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)k+m} = \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)n+m+1} - pn.$$

Proof. For $n \geq 0$, $k \geq 1$, and any nonnegative integer m , we have the following recurrence relation:

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,k(p+1)+m} = \mathcal{L}_{p,k(p+1)+m+1} - \mathcal{L}_{p,(k-1)(p+1)+m+1} - p.$$

Then, we do the following computation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{k=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,k(p+1)+m} &= \mathcal{L}_{p,m} + \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)+m} + \mathcal{L}_{p,2(p+1)+m} + \cdots + \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)n+m} \\
 &= \mathcal{L}_{p,m} + (\mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)+m+1} - \mathcal{L}_{p,m+1} - p) \\
 &\quad + (\mathcal{L}_{p,2(p+1)+m+1} - \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)+m+1} - p) \\
 &\quad + \cdots + (\mathcal{L}_{p,n(p+1)+m+1} - \mathcal{L}_{p,(n-1)(p+1)+m+1} - p) \\
 &= \mathcal{L}_{p,n(p+1)+m+1} + \mathcal{L}_{p,m} - \mathcal{L}_{p,m+1} - np.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

We consider the expression $\mathcal{L}_{p,m} - \mathcal{L}_{p,m+1}$ next.

For $m = 0, 1, \dots, p - 1$,

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,m} - \mathcal{L}_{p,m+1} = 1 - 1 = 0. \tag{3}$$

□

Corollary 1. For $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)k+p} = \mathcal{L}_{p,(p+1)(n+1)} - p(n+1) - 1.$$

Proof. For $m = p$ in Theorem 2, we have

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,m} - \mathcal{L}_{p,m+1} = 1 - (p+2) = -p - 1. \tag{4}$$

We get the desired result by substituting (3) and (4) into (2). □

Remark 3. If we take $p = 1$ in Theorem 2 and Corollary 1, we get the identities

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{k=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,2k} &= \mathcal{L}_{p,2n+1} - n, \\
 \sum_{k=0}^n \mathcal{L}_{p,2k+1} &= \mathcal{L}_{p,2n+2} - (n+2),
 \end{aligned}$$

which are given in [5, Proposition 3.1 (2)-(3)].

To obtain the Binet formula of the Leonardo p -sequence, we use the Binet formula of the Fibonacci p -sequence (see [1])

$$F_{p,n} = \sum_{k=1}^{p+1} \frac{\alpha_k^n}{(p+1)\alpha_k - p},$$

where α_k are the distincts roots of the polynomial $x^{p+1} - x^p - 1$.

Theorem 3. *The Binet formula of the Leonardo p -sequence is*

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n} = (p + 1) \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p+1} \frac{\alpha_k^{n+1}}{(p + 1)\alpha_k - p} \right) - p.$$

Proof. From Theorem 1 and the Binet formula of Fibonacci p -sequence, we get the desired result. \square

In the following theorem, we give the Honsberger formula for the Leonardo p -numbers. We need the following identity which is the Honsberger-like identity for Fibonacci p -numbers [16]:

$$F_{p,m+n} = F_{p,m}F_{p,n+1} + \sum_{j=1}^p F_{p,m-j}F_{p,n-p+j}$$

where m and n are nonnegative integers such that $m, n \geq p$.

Theorem 4. *For nonnegative integers $m, n \geq p$, we have*

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{L}_{p,m}\mathcal{L}_{p,n+1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \mathcal{L}_{p,m-j}\mathcal{L}_{p,n-p+j} \\ &= (p + 1) \left(\mathcal{L}_{p,m+n+1} - p \sum_{j=0}^p (F_{p,m-j+1} + F_{p,n-p+j+2}) + p(p + 1) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By using Theorem 1 and the Honsberger identity for Fibonacci p -numbers, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{L}_{p,m}\mathcal{L}_{p,n+1} + \sum_{j=1}^p \mathcal{L}_{p,m-j}\mathcal{L}_{p,n-p+j} \\ &= (p + 1)^2 F_{p,m+1}F_{p,n+2} - p(p + 1) (F_{p,m+1} + F_{p,n+2}) + p^2 \\ &+ (p + 1)^2 \sum_{j=1}^p F_{p,m-j+1}F_{p,n+j-p+1} - p(p + 1) \sum_{j=1}^p (F_{p,m-j+1} + F_{p,n+j-p+1}) + \sum_{j=1}^p p^2 \\ &= (p + 1)^2 \left(F_{p,m+1}F_{p,n+2} + \sum_{j=1}^p F_{p,m-j+1}F_{p,n-p+j+1} \right) \\ &- p(p + 1) \left(F_{p,m+1} + F_{p,n+2} + \sum_{j=1}^p (F_{p,m-j+1} + F_{p,n-p+j+1}) \right) + p^2(p + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (p + 1)^2 F_{p,m+n+2} - p(p + 1) \left(\sum_{j=0}^p F_{p,m-j+1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p+1} F_{p,n-p+j+1} \right) + p^2 (p + 1) \\
 &= (p + 1) \left((p + 1) F_{p,m+n+2} - p + p - p \sum_{j=0}^p (F_{p,m-j+1} + F_{p,n-p+j+2}) + p^2 \right) \\
 &= (p + 1) \left(\mathcal{L}_{p,m+n+1} - p \sum_{j=0}^p (F_{p,m-j+1} + F_{p,n-p+j+2}) + p(p + 1) \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 4. For $p = 1$ in Theorem 4, we get the following identity for the Leonardo numbers:

$$\mathcal{L}_m \mathcal{L}_{n+1} + \mathcal{L}_{m-1} \mathcal{L}_n = 2\mathcal{L}_{m+n+1} - \mathcal{L}_{m+1} - \mathcal{L}_{n+2} + 2.$$

3. Incomplete Leonardo p -numbers

In this section, we define incomplete Leonardo p -numbers and state some properties of these numbers. For this purpose, first we consider the Theorem 1, then we need to use the definition of incomplete Fibonacci p -numbers [15]:

$$F_{p,n}(k) = \sum_{i=0}^k \binom{n-pi-1}{i}, \quad 0 \leq k \leq \left\lfloor \frac{n-1}{p+1} \right\rfloor.$$

Definition 2. Let n be a positive integer and k be an integer. For $0 \leq k \leq \left\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \right\rfloor$, the incomplete Leonardo p -numbers are defined as

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k) = (p + 1) \sum_{i=0}^k \binom{n-pi}{i} - p.$$

It is clear to see the following special cases:

- $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(0) = 1$,
- $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(1) = (p + 1)(n - p) + 1$,
- $\mathcal{L}_{p,n} \left(\left\lfloor \frac{n}{p+1} \right\rfloor \right) = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}$.

Proposition 3. For $0 \leq k \leq \frac{n-p-2}{p+1}$, the non-linear recurrence relation of the incomplete Leonardo p -numbers $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k)$ is

$$\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k + 1) = \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}(k + 1) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k) + p.$$

Proof. By using the definition of incomplete Leonardo p -numbers, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}(k+1) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k) + p \\
 &= (p+1) \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \binom{n-pi-1}{i} - p + (p+1) \sum_{i=0}^k \binom{n-p(i+1)-1}{i} - p + p \\
 &= (p+1) \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \binom{n-pi-1}{i} - p + (p+1) \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} \binom{n-pi-1}{i-1} \\
 &= (p+1) \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \left(\binom{n-pi-1}{i} + \binom{n-pi-1}{i-1} \right) - p \\
 &= (p+1) \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \binom{n-pi}{i} - p = \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k+1).
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Proposition 3 can be transformed into the following non-homogeneous recurrence relation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k) &= \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}(k) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k-1) + p \\
 &= \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}(k) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k) + p + (\mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k-1) - \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k)) \\
 &= \mathcal{L}_{p,n-1}(k) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p-1}(k) + p - (p+1) \binom{n-p(k+1)-1}{k}. \tag{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4. For $0 \leq k \leq \frac{n-p-s}{p+1}$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^s \binom{s}{i} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+pi}(k+i) + (2^s - 1)p = \mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)s}(k+s).$$

Proof. The proof will be done by using induction on s . From Proposition 3, the relation is true for $s = 0$ and $s = 1$. Assume that the relation is true for all $j < s + 1$. Now we show that it is true for $s + 1$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \binom{s+1}{i} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+pi}(k+i) \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \left[\binom{s}{i} + \binom{s}{i-1} \right] \mathcal{L}_{p,n+pi}(k+i)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{i=0}^s \binom{s}{i} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+pi}(k+i) + \sum_{i=0}^{s+1} \binom{s}{i-1} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+pi}(k+i) \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^s \binom{s}{i} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+pi}(k+i) + \sum_{i=0}^s \binom{s}{i} \mathcal{L}_{p,n+p(i+1)}(k+i+1) \\
 &= \mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)s}(k+s) - (2^s - 1)p + \mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)s+p}(k+s+1) - (2^s - 1)p \\
 &= \mathcal{L}_{p,n+(p+1)(s+1)}(k+s+1) - (2^{s+1} - 1)p.
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Note that when $p = 1$ in Proposition 4, we obtain

$$\sum_{i=0}^s \binom{s}{i} \mathcal{L}_{n+i}(k+i) + 2^s - 1 = \mathcal{L}_{n+2s}(k+s),$$

which is given in [11, Equation (3.4)].

Proposition 5. For $n \geq (p + 1)(k + 1)$ we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^{s-1} \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p+i}(k) + sp = \mathcal{L}_{p,n+s}(k+1) - \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k+1).$$

Proof. We prove it by using induction on s . It is clear to see that the equality holds for $s = 1$. Suppose that it is true for all $i < s$. Now we prove it for s . From Proposition 3, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{L}_{p,n+s+1}(k+1) - \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k+1) \\
 &= (\mathcal{L}_{p,n+s}(k+1) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n+s-p}(k) + p) - \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k+1) \\
 &= (\mathcal{L}_{p,n+s}(k+1) - \mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k+1)) + \mathcal{L}_{p,n+s-p}(k) + p \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^{s-1} \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p+i}(k) + sp + \mathcal{L}_{p,n+s-p}(k) + p \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^s \mathcal{L}_{p,n-p+i}(k) + p(s+1),
 \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof. □

Remark 5. If we take $p = 1$ in Proposition 3, Proposition 4, Equation (5), and Proposition 5, then we get the results in [6, Proposition 1-4], respectively.

Finally, we note that the generating function of incomplete Leonardo p -numbers can be obtained by using the generating function of incomplete Fibonacci p -numbers which is given in [15, Theorem 16] as:

$$R_p^k(t) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} F_{p,n}(k) t^n = \frac{t^{k(p+1)+1}}{(1-t-t^{p+1})} \times \left[F_{p,k(p+1)+1} + \sum_{i=1}^p (F_{p,k(p+1)+i+1} - F_{p,k(p+1)+i}) t^i - \frac{t^{p+1}}{(1-t)^{k+1}} \right].$$

Since $\mathcal{L}_{p,n}(k) = (p+1)F_{p,n+1}(k) - p$, we get the desired result.

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